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Klaibya: Ayurvedic concept of erectile dysfunction: A critical Review

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Arun Shankarrao Dudhamal,

H.O.D. and Associate Professor, Rog-Nidan Dept., Ayurved College,

Sion, Mumbai-400022, Maharashtra, India

Author Correspondence: Mob.: 9664340199 Email: asdudhamal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: “Erectile dysfunction” is a common condition associated with aging, chronic illnesses and various modifiable risk factors. It has been estimated that the prevalence of erectile dysfunction of all degrees is 52% in men 40 to 70 years old, with higher rates in those older than 70 years. Such type of diseased condition is described in *ayurved* classical text in the name of disease called “*Klaubya*”. *Klaibya* is caused due to *Dusht Shukra Dhatu*. The causes of *Shukra Dushti*. In Charak Samhita five types *Klaubya* are viz. 1) *Bijoupgataj*, 2) *Dhajoupgataj*, 3) *Jarasambhavaj*, 4) *Shukra kshayaj*, 5) *Shandhaj* and *Sushrut Samhita* four types of *kaubya* are viz. 1) *Asekya*, 2) *Soughandhik*, 3) *Kumbhik* and 4) *Irshik*.

Aim and objects of this *Klaibya: Ayurvedic* concept of erectile dysfunction. In this study concluded that many types of *Klaibya* as erectile dysfunctions are described in classical text. On the clinical findings the symptoms and treatment may play a important role according to these types.

KEYWORD: *Klaibya*, erectile dysfunction, *Shukra Dhatu*, sexual dysfunction

INTRODUCTION:

Hindu mythology *dharm*, *arth*, *kam* and *moksha* these are the four *Purusharth* [Pillar] of the life. *Ayurved* science adopted this concept. Healthy life is essential for achievement of these *Purusharth*. After age of Puberty we are bonded for achievement of *kam* [Sexual life]. The healthy sexual life is hampered by some organic disorders of penis in male these are considered under *Klaibya* or erectile dysfunction of penis^[1].

Erectile dysfunction is a common condition associated with aging, chronic illnesses and various modifiable risk factors. Normal penile erection is a hemodynamic process that is dependent on corporal smooth muscle relaxation mediated by parasympathetic neurotransmission, nitric oxide, and possibly other regulatory factors and electrophysiological events.^[8]

Aim and Object:

Aim and objects of this study is to rule out the importance of concept of *Klaibya* as erectile dysfunction described in *Ayurved*.

Material and Method: From *Ayurvedic* compendia, basic principles of *Sadyasadyatva* (Prognosis of disease),

Antarvegi and *Bahirvegi Jwar lakshanas* are reviewed in perspective of evaluation of *Antarvegi* and *Bahirvegi Jwar Lakshana* in *sadhyasadyatva*.

- Published journals related to subject, update information available on internet is critically analyzed and assessed
- Modern literature regarding Prognosis of disease is reviewed.

A] Literature search:

Definition:

Klaibya is defined as sexual dysfunction characterized by the inability to develop or maintain an erection of the penis during sexual performance.^[1]

Causes:

Charaka described *Klaibya* is caused due to *Dusht Shukra Dhatu*. The causes of *Shukra Dushti* are as follows:

Heavy exercise, excessive sexual activities, consumption of unwholesome food, intercourse at premature age, indulging sex with animals other than women, controlling semen during ejaculation, excessive intake of foods which are dry, bitter in taste, astringent,

salt, sour and hot. Intercourse with impassionate women, old age, fear, anger, worry, grief, lack of confidence in partner, injury to genital organ by sharp instruments, alkalis, cauterization, black magic, sever emaciation due to chronic diseases, suppression of natural urges, injuries and vitiation in *Dhatu*.^[1]

Due these factors *Shukra Dhatu* becomes vitiated which causes *Klaibya*.

Following eight faults in *Shukra Dhatu* also causes *Klaibya*.^[1]

1	<i>Fenil</i>	Frothy
2	<i>Tanu</i>	Thin
3	<i>Ruksha</i>	Rough or Ununctuous
4	<i>Vivarna</i>	Discoloration in semen
5	<i>Puti</i>	Foul smell semen
6	<i>Pichil</i>	Slimy semen
7	<i>Anyadhatup-sansrushta</i>	Semen contaminated with other Dhatu
8	<i>Avasadi</i>	After ejaculation person become tired.

Vitiated Doshaj characteristics of Shukra Dhatu:

Due to vitiated *Vaat Dosh* the semen become frothy, thin and the sexual activities become painful and scanty semen is ejaculated. Vitiated *vaataj Shukra* unable to conceive.^[1]

Due to vitiated *Pitta Dosh* the semen turns in blue or yellow colored, foul smelled, thin in viscosity and hot in touch.^[1]

Due to vitiated *Kaph Dosh* obstruct the path of *Shukra-vah Srotas* which causes excessive slimy semen.^[1]

Excessive intercourse, trauma etc are causes ulcers in *Shukra-vah Srotas* which causes blood contaminated semen^[1]

Suppression of natural urges like micturation, defecation etc. causes aggravation of *Vaat Dosh*, which causes spasmodic obstruction in *Shukravah Srotas*. After ejaculation of this vitiated *shukra*, the person become tired, so it is called as *Avasadi*.^[1]

Characteristics of Pure Shukra:

Oily, thick, slimy, Sweet, non-corrosive and crystal like are the characteristics of pure *shukra Dhatu*. The smell of pure *shukra* is sweat like honey.^[2]

Common symptoms of Klaiby:

Willing to do intercourse with stunner women but penis doesn't get erection. Therefore the person becomes unable to do intercourse. He suffers from *dyspnoea* and excessive sweating. His penis become loose and without semen. These are the

common symptoms of *Klaibya* ^[2]

Types of *Klaiby* ^[11]:

Sr. No.	Charak Samhita	Sushrut Samhita
1	<i>Bijouphataj</i>	<i>Asekya</i>
2	<i>Dhajouphataj</i>	<i>Soughandhik</i>
3	<i>Jarasambhavaj</i>	<i>Kumbhik</i>
4	<i>Shukra kshayaj</i>	<i>Irshik</i>
5	-	<i>Shandhaj</i>

1) *Bijouphataj Klaibya*:

Aggravated Dosha viatiated the semen and diminished in quantity which causes *Bijouphataj Klaibya*. The symptoms of *Bijouphataj Klaibya* are Paleness, weakness, low in vitality, less excitement with women, Heart diseases, Asthama, Joundice, physical exhaustion, vomiting, diarrhea, colic pain and fever. ^[1]

2) *Dhajouphataj Klaibya*:

Swelling, pain and redness of phallus, appearance of boils and inflammation of penis, fleshy growth in the phallus and quick ulcerations, exudation which appear like rice-water or which is brownish black or pink in color, bid thirst, giddiness, fainting, and vomiting. Red, black, blue, turbid liquid colored discharge from urethra, acute burning sensation and pain

in the loin and groin region. Some time slimy, pale yellow discharge is occurred. Mild swelling of phallus with suppurates, sloughy and scanty discharge with maggots formation are the symptoms of *Dhajouphataj Klaibya*. ^[1]

3) *Jarasambhavaj Klaibya*:

Jaghanya [Childhood], Madhya [young age] and Pravar [Old age] are the three stages of age. *Jarasambhavaj klaibya* is occurred due to diminished condition of *shukra Dhatu*. ^[1]

If Rasayan and vajikar treatment not taken properly in young age; the person losses his physical and mental strength. All Rasadi dhatu become diminished and ultimately it resulted in *Shukra-kshya*. General weakness, discoloration, fainting are occurred and person become impotence. ^[15]

4) *Shukra-Kshayaj Klaibya*:

Anulom [increasing order Ras-Rakt-Mans....] or Pratilom [decreasing order *Shukra-Majja Asthi..*] causes leads to cause less quantity of *Shukra dhatu* in body. This pathology of moderately loss of *Shukra dhatu* leads to impotency which is called as *Shukra Kshayaj Klaibya*. ^[1]

5) *Janmjat Klaibya*:

Morbidity of sperm of father and ovum of mother and because of sinful work during past life, during embryonic stage, the aggravated dosha afflict the channel carrying sperm, and make it atrophid. Because of this, [or in later part of life] the process of semen formation in offspring is inhibited. The man developed with full organs but remains emaciated. This impotency is known as Janmjat-Klaiby [congenital].^[1]

Prognosis of Klaibya:

Klaiby occurred due to *Dhvajbhanga*, *Janmjat* and *Kshayaj* are incurable. *Dhvajbhanga* *klaiby* occurred due to amputation of phallus or testicles are to be considered as incurable.

Description of *Klaiby* by *Sushruta*:

Asekya, *Soughandhik*, *Kubhik*, *Irshik* and *Shandhya* are the five types of *Klaibya* described by *Sushruta*. All first are having presence of semen but *Shukra Dhatu* is absent in *Shandha* type. The details of these *Klaibya* is as follows.^[2]

1) *Asekya*^[2]:

Due to diminished *Shukra Dhatu* in father and mother, offspring not getting erection in penis during intercourse. If he swallows semen then he gets erections.^[3]

2) *Soughandhik*^[2]:

When a person got birth from suppurated vagina, he will get erection in penis by smell of vagina or penis, and then he get erections in penis.^[4]

3) *Kubhik*^[2]:

The person who doing anal coitus with women is known as *Kubhik*^[6,7]

4) *Irshik*^[2]:

Those who are getting penile erection after seeing other sex is known as *Irshik*.^[6,7]

5) *Shandha*^[2]:

When man having sex with women in menstrual cycle then his male offspring look like and behavior like female this person is called as *Shandha*^[6,7]

B) Type of study–Fundamental study

Discussion:

Klaibya is caused due to *Dusht Shukra Dhatu*. The causes of *Shukra Dushti*. In *Charak Samhita* five types *Klaubya* are viz. 1) *Bijouphataj*, 2) *Dhajouphataj*, 3) *Jarasambhavaj*, 4) *Shukra kshayaj*, 5) *Shandhaj* and *Sushrut Samhita* four types of *kaubya* are viz. 1) *Asekya*, 2) *Soughandhik*, 3) *Kumbhik*, 4) *Irshik*.

Conclusion:

Klaibya: Ayurvedic concept of erectile dysfunction. In this study concluded that many types of *Klaibya* as erectile dysfunctions are described in classical text. On the clinical findings the symptoms and treatment may play a important role according to these types.

References:

1. Vaidya Yadavaji Trikamji Acharya, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha elaborated by Charaka & Drudhabala with Ayurveda Dipika Commentary by Chakrapanidatta, Varanasi Choukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Reprinted 2005, chikitsa stan 30
2. Anantram Sharma, Sushrut Samhita, Varanasi, Choukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, 1st Edition 2001
3. Pt. Hari Sadashiva Shastri Paradkar Ashtanga Hridaya of Vagbhata Annotated by Dr. Anna Kunte & Krishna Navre, Varanasi Choukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Reprinted 2002
4. 'Madhav Nidan' of Madhavakara with 'Atank Darpan' commentary by

Vachaspati Mishra and 'Madhukosh' commentary by Vijayrakshit and 'Vidyotini' hindi commentary by Sudarshanshastri published by Chaukhamba Surbharati Publication, Gopal Mandir lane, Varanasi-2002

5. Dr. Subhash Ranade, Dr. Sunanda Randade, Concept of Pathology in Ayurveda, Reprint edition, Pune, Narendra Prakashan, 2006
6. Dr. Pavana Jayaram, Dr. manoj Sankaranarayana, Roga Vijnana and Vikriti Vijnana, First Edition, Varanasi, Chowkhamba Sankrit Series Office, 2014, P-28-29.
7. Dr. P. S. Byadgi, Ayurvediya Vikriti Vijnana and Roga Vijnana, First edition, Varanasi, Choukhamba Publication, 2009. P163
8. ARNOLD MELMAN, J. CLIVE GINGELL The Journal of Urology, January 1999; Volume 161, Issue 1, Pages 5-11; url: [http://www.jurology.com/article/S0022-5347\(01\)62045-7/abstract](http://www.jurology.com/article/S0022-5347(01)62045-7/abstract) DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0022-5347\(01\)62045-7](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0022-5347(01)62045-7)

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